

**A TEAM APPROACH TO IMPROVING RELIABILITY,
AVAILABILITY, MAINTAINABILITY AND TESTABILITY (RAM&T) REQUIREMENTS**

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Abstract

This paper is a case study pertaining to the application of a "teaming" approach to problem solving in resolving reliability, availability, maintainability, and testability (RAM&T) issues at the U.S. Army Communications-Electronic Command (CECOM), Fort Monmouth, New Jersey. The evolutionary growth of the Reliability, Availability, Maintainability Enhancement of Communications-Electronic Systems (RAMECES) Task Force at CECOM suggests interdisciplinary groups can work together and focus on a common task. RAMECES has proven to be an effective way to address complex RAM&T issues in a shrinking and demographically changing work environment. A RAMECES-type "teaming" approach to addressing complex issues will enable the Army to increase productivity and meet the threat of a constantly changing global political environment.

Introduction

Does teaming as a management resource work? More specifically, what is its potential to succeed in a government organization? Can teams work across disciplines? Can the team be comprised of members within a particular Department of Defense component and operate cross functionally? Given the highly competitive, individualistic American character, can teaming within the work place be both creative and productive? If the answers to these questions are yes, then what are the factors that contribute to the successful implementation of teaming endeavors within government agencies?

H.B. Karp's paper entitled, Team Building From A Gestalt Perspective, defines teaming, lists its essential elements, explains factors contributing to group dynamics, and argues for the necessity of teams.¹ To paraphrase this author, a team is comprised of a group of people working together to obtain objectives of their own and those of their organization. Reilly and Jones also cite the four "essential elements" of a team.² The discussion of these elements have been molded into questions pertaining to RAMECES endeavors: (1) Did task force members have a chartered reason for working together? (2) Did the complementary expertise of RAMECES Task Force members enable the members to reach agreement on mission objectives? (3) Did the individual approach to solving reliability, availability, maintainability, and testability (RAM&T) issues prove to be adequate? and (4) Was the product of the task force in demand by the Communications-Electronic Command (CECOM), the Ft. Monmouth community and other Army activities?

The Team Approach

The Army needs a RAMECES-type task force to shore up a mission area of responsibility during down-sizing and a changing demographic period. Operational and Support cost savings result from Task Force members finding solutions to complex problems that one individual working alone could not. Using the RAMECES Task Force as a case study, I will demonstrate that "teaming" as a management tool works.

Teaming as a management approach has been the fundamental basis of the RAMECES Task Force at CECOM since September, 1988. Just prior to this time Mr. Lorber, then Deputy Chief of Staff for Product

Assurance, Headquarters, Army Materiel Command (AMC) and Mr. Martin Burger, then acting Director, Product Assurance and Test Directorate, CECOM, recognized certain deficiencies within the RAM&T discipline. They then envisioned a process action team as a vehicle to address these deficiencies.

As a result, the Hardware and Software Tiger Teams were established at Fort Monmouth in September, 1988, to address new approaches to these disciplines in Army contracting. The merger of the Hardware and Software Tiger Teams occurred in the Fall, 1989. Around the same time, Billy M. Thomas, then Commanding General of Fort Monmouth, chartered RAMECES as a formal organizational entity. Shortly thereafter the designation "Tiger Teams" was changed to "Task Force" in light of RAMECES's expanding role to address RAM&T issues early-on in a system's life cycle. Most recently, it has become a staff activity within the Concurrent Engineering Directorate (CED), with its chairmanship institutionalized under that directorate. This scenario of events was provided to show that "teaming" as a management tool does work. The longevity of RAMECES, as well as the Task Force's ability to effectively have members from the readiness and research and development communities work together to solve complex problems indicate that "teaming" as a management tool has a future at Fort Monmouth, and possibly throughout the U.S. Army. Management receptivity to RAMECES, briefed at the four star level, at Major Subordinate Commands other than CECOM, and at AMC Commander Conferences remains positive.

The RAMECES Task Force's ability to resolve both hardware and software RAM&T issues at Fort Monmouth demonstrates its effectiveness as a management tool. Today, it is imperative to ask whether or not the Army can accomplish its missions without adopting a "teaming approach" during the current army "down-sizing." Down-sizing has the potential to rapidly reduce the size of the total active army force from just under 700,000 to less than 500,000 personnel by 1997. Although recent global socio-political circumstances have changed Army strategy, its mission to deter aggression has not changed. Managers responsible for ensuring that Army missions are met, find that the "survivors" who remain are overwhelmed with the increased work load and diminished resources needed to complete tasks.

Compounding this problem is the reality of the changing demographics of the work place. Experienced personnel, with a wealth of corporate knowledge, are retiring or leaving federal service. To this end, the RAMECES Task Force has helped to fill the void left by those departing, by coupling the "teaming" effort and pooling resources to improve RAM&T contractual requirements at CECOM. In addition, RAMECES has been able to sustain task force initiated projects. Through such endeavors, RAMECES has become recognized as a center of RAM&T expertise by Project Managers and functional activities, who often suddenly find themselves confronted with complex issues for which they need RAMECES' expertise to resolve. As RAMECES' reputation grew, so did its scope of work. Called upon to address a variety of issues, the Task Force frequently functioned as a "special project" office which sometimes confronted RAM&T issues only tangentially related to its charter. One such issue was developing a new statement of work pertaining to incoming inspection procedures.

Other RAM&T technologies for which RAMECES provided hardware and software RAM&T requirements are

fault tolerant architecture, microwave technology insertion, and hardware description language demonstration and verification. All required bottom-up rethinking and proved that a focussed "teaming" approach to resolve complex issues works.

Since its beginning, the RAMECES Task Force has been interdisciplinary by intent. As a horizontal integrated design and implementation program, the RAMECES organization includes members from fifteen CECOM and non-CECOM organizations, including the Logistic Technology Center, Center for Software Engineering, research and development centers of AMC Major Subordinate Commands, and the U.S. Army, CECOM, Intelligence Materiel Management centers. The success of the thirty-five member task force in improving RAM&T requirements at CECOM stems largely from its adoption of Total Quality Management (TQM) as a *modus operandi*. This helped ensure that representatives from readiness organizations and research and development centers addressed hardware and software RAM&T requirements early in the product life cycle.

The team effort succeeded in establishing RAM&T requirements in numerous developmental programs. These key programs could not have been realized without TQM, or the collective effort of RAMECES team members. By combining the expertise of its individual members in a single team effort, greater Army organizational goals are achieved. The long established myth of functional "stove piping" within the Army bureaucracy was shattered by the RAMECES experience. The early implementation of RAM&T, and periodic review throughout a systems life cycle, demands the attention that only an inter-disciplinary, cross functional, highly synergistic team such as RAMECES could provide.

Skeptics of the team approach to problem solving maintain that on a limited, short term basis, RAMECES-type procedures may work, but they see the individualistic and competitive American character undercutting such practices in the long run. Arm chair sociologists will point to cultures such as Japan, China, and Korea, which successfully demonstrate a long standing history of a well-disciplined work force which values conformity to the group above those of individuals. The recent Japanese predominance in automobile and commercial electronic manufacturing further appears to provide convincing to support their arguments pertaining to the collective nature of these societies. Proponents of the "this can't be done in America" attitude correctly point to the fact that in cultures such as these, the pronoun "I" has no representation in the indigenous language of these countries.

Paradoxically, for the Army and possibly for American society to meet the challenges of the 21st century, a teaming approach to problem solving becomes critical. To adopt a RAMECES-type task force does not imply that individual expertise is no longer valued. On the contrary, the "teaming" approach to problem solving only helps to optimize individual expertise by exposing team members to others from similar backgrounds. In turn, team members act as catalysts for innovative thinking in the problem solving process. The Army's success in Desert Shield/Storm, and the success of long standing organizations such as the Salvation Army and Catholic Charities, suggest anything but an apathetic attitude towards "teaming" on the part of Americans. Being committed to the organization which it serves means that the RAMECES Task Force members never lose sight of their ultimate customer: the soldier.

Let us not confuse the American displeasure for submissive behavior as an unwillingness to work collectively for an organizational goal. The success of the Japanese in automobile production may have not occurred if it were not for the export of American management techniques to Japan by Deming.

Key to the RAMECES Task Force success, and probably the success of any teaming endeavor, is management endorsement and support. The complexity of modern communications-electronic systems means that no single organization can anticipate all the potential RAM&T deficiencies of a requirement. Upper management understood both the need to improve the way CECOM contracts for RAM&T requirements and to adopt a "teaming," TQM approach to problem solving. They realized the traditional obstacles to change such as parochial self-interest, misunderstanding, lack of trust, different assessments of a situation, and low tolerance for change, had to be overcome in some instances. Once a briefing was approved by the acting Director, Product Assurance & Test, CECOM, each of the directors of the command received a "desk-side chat" on RAMECES goals. Each Director was asked to provide a representative with an alternate task force member who could collectively contribute six to ten hours a week to improve RAM&T at CECOM by participating in RAMECES Task Force projects. Before long, most of the directorates at CECOM had representatives attending RAMECES meetings. Once this CECOM core group was established, tenant organizations co-located at Ft. Monmouth were briefed in the same manner, followed by briefings to other AMC major subordinate commands. Many of these organizations complied with the RAMECES chairman's request for personnel support. The support the RAMECES Task Force received from the management of member organizations helped to sustain participation in the group, as well as create a positive working environment for change.

This hand-in-glove relationship between the RAMECES Task Force and management was self-reinforcing. Management interest in support of RAMECES continued to grow as representatives of industry were invited to speak and share ideas on RAM&T and TQM with the task force members. Concurrently, subcommittees were established within the task force to begin to address the ninety-nine RAM&T issues brainstormed by the total RAMECES membership. When the directors and directorate personnel better understood the scope of issues being addressed by the RAMECES Task Force, receptivity to RAMECES endeavors within the Army community increased substantially. RAMECES was able to initiate projects and take required corrective action to address RAM&T deficiencies, in large part due to the monies and resources provided by members organizations. The Director of Command, Control, and Communications, CECOM, for example, provided funding on relatively short notice for state-of-charge meters for lithium batteries in response to a request from the field during Desert Storm. This support would have not materialized if RAMECES had failed to act proactively with respect to a lithium battery deficiency and did not keep management informed of its activity.

Without doubt, management support is the key to successful "team building" efforts within government and industry alike. However, it takes the resolve of the "movers and shakers" at all levels of management to implement change. Managers across the country increasingly understand the importance of RAMECES-type teaming efforts if they wish to have their organizations remain economically sound and technologically viable into the next century.

Conclusion

RAMECES-type initiatives within the Army and American industry can begin to recapture the collective energy and consciousness that gave rise to a management system emulated the world over. The teaming disposition of Americans has also provided a government system that has helped to maintain world peace through one of the more successful teams in the world, the U.S. Army.

RAMECES as a teaming effort at CECOM succeeded because it was able to function as an independent, chartered organization with a minimum of management interference, and because it was able to pool together personnel and material resources from numerous Army organizations. Parochial interests, for the most part, were held at bay, since task force members well understood that the changing work environment, and the complexity of state-of-the-art technology meant that no organization could provide solutions to the numerous RAM&T deficiencies associated with communications-electronic equipment. In other words, the synergy of the RAMECES Task Force was greater than the sum of its parts. The hands-off approach of upper management encouraged the RAMECES organization to work closely together, define their individual roles within the task force, define areas of responsibility, and self-impose group values which allowed task force objectives to be met in a congenial working environment.

About the Author:

Dr. Vacante is the former chairman of the RAMECES Task Force, Fort Monmouth, New Jersey. Prior to June 1992 he worked as a Quality Assurance Section Chief in the Concurrent Engineering Directorate (CED). As a CED staff member he developed policies, procedures, and guidance for reliability, maintainability, testability and quality assurance issues. Dr. Vacante is also the chairman of the Standards Subcommittee, to the Reliability, Maintainability, and Supportability G-11 committee, of the Society of Automotive Engineers, and a member of the Rapid Insertion of Electronic Technology (RIET) committee, Office of the Director of Defense Research and Engineering. He recently was appointed to the position of Professor of Contracting and Acquisition Management at the Army Management Staff College, Fort Belvoir.

End Notes

1. H.B. Karp, "Team Building From A Gestalt Perspective," The 1980 Annual Handbook for Group Facilitators, University Associates, San Diego, California, 1980, pp. 157-160.
2. Ibid. p.167.
3. John M. Ivaneceovich, James H. Donnelly, Jr., and James L. Gibson, Management Principles and Functions, 1989, Ch.7, p 576.